

Integration of Educational Mobile Applications in Facilitating Learner-Centered Instructional Strategies at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of mobile applications into higher education has transformed learner-centered instructional methodologies by enabling personalized, interactive, and contextual learning environments. This study explores how mobile applications foster active learning, knowledge production, social interaction, and scaffolding, thereby boosting student engagement and accommodating diverse learning styles. Mobile applications support collaborative learning, offer immersive experiences through augmented reality, and provide real-world problem-solving exercises aligned with constructivist principles. The recommendations emphasize the strategic integration of comprehensive curricula and institutional support, the development of customizable and accessible learning platforms, collaboration with developers for localized and secure solutions, ongoing monitoring and evaluation, digital literacy enhancement, cooperation and peer learning, and the promotion of lifelong learning skills to ensure a successful learning experience in Nigerian tertiary education.

Keyword: Mobile Applications, Learner-Centered Approaches, Active Learning, Knowledge Construction, Social Interaction, Contextual Learning

Introduction

Higher education has seen a transformational shift in recent years due to technological integration, particularly the widespread use of mobile applications. These applications have emerged as formidable tools, revolutionizing the teaching and learning experience. The adoption of mobile applications to facilitate learner-centered teaching marks a significant paradigm shifts in higher education methodologies (Bakar, 2021; Tan, 2018). As institutions endeavor to address the diverse needs of 21st-century learners, mobile applications provide a versatile and accessible means to establish interactive and engaging learning environments.

Learning involves linking information sources to create a network. In the present day, individuals need to possess the capability to identify connections, discern patterns, and make sense of various fields, ideas, and concepts (Goldie, 2016). Given the changes in the current learning environment, it is crucial to reevaluate learning support. This recognition stems from the understanding that today's world is significantly distinct from the world in which our teaching and learning methods were initially developed (Neck & Greene, 2011). We are now in an era marked by swift transformations in transportation and communication infrastructures, altering the way and speed at which we conduct activities. Moreover, the volume of available information is growing exponentially, the very nature of knowledge is evolving, and the world is undergoing rapid changes due to the sometimes conflicting but often complementary processes of globalization and localism (Baker & Powell, 2024).

Education aims to shape students into active, competitive contributors to society by fostering cultural grounding, global proactivity, scientific thinking, professional skills, and a commitment to faith and justice. Recognizing the limits of classroom education, we focus on nurturing lifelong learners who are independent, analytical, reflective, and proactive. Our goal is for students to take responsibility for their personal growth amid societal changes (Pendergast et al., 2005). Meeting

these demands requires a new learning environment with essential resources and a participatory, critical, and creative teaching approach (Amhag, 2016).

Mobile Devices Used at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Mobile devices encompass a variety of portable computing tools and software applications that allow users to perform tasks without being confined to a specific location (Roth, 2024). This category includes smartphones, tablets, wearable devices, mobile operating systems, and mobile applications (Pereira & Rodrigues, 2013). These devices are noted for their portability, connectivity, and capability to access and process information on the move (Schrock, 2015). They offer ubiquitous connectivity and access to information via wireless communication networks and portable devices, emphasizing their core attributes of ubiquity, connectivity, and portability (Goldena, 2023). Mobile learning (M-learning) introduces flexibility to educational activities by removing time and place constraints. Mobile tools such as laptops, mobile phones, smartphones, PDAs, and MP3 players are integral to m-learning (Bostan et al., 2021). Due to their multi-functionality, mobile devices have become indispensable in modern education. They enhance the learning experience by offering flexibility, enabling real-time communication, and supporting collaborative and personalized learning environments. As higher education evolves, the integration of mobile devices is expected to play a crucial role in shaping future teaching and learning methodologies.

Educational Mobile Applications Used at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Mobile applications have become integral to daily life, significantly impacting education (Lee & Chan, 2007; Pang, 2024). At the tertiary level, these applications act as catalysts for learner-centered approaches, shifting the focus from traditional teacher-centric models to pedagogies that empower students as active participants in their learning journeys (Alam & Mohanty, 2023). Mobile applications in education foster collaborative learning environments and provide personalized learning pathways, enhancing student engagement, promoting critical thinking, and accommodating diverse learning styles (McQuiggan et al., 2015). In this context, educational technology plays a crucial role, with mobile learning tools offering significant advantages by aligning technology with content and pedagogy. Educators' effective integration of these tools is critical to enhancing teaching and learning outcomes (Bostan et al., 2021).

Educational mobile applications are designed to facilitate learning through interactive and engaging experiences. These apps serve various purposes, such as providing access to educational content, teaching resources, and tools for both formal and informal learning (Belle, 2024). They cover a wide range of topics and skills, from early childhood education to university-level courses, vocational training, and professional development (Noguera, 2024). Common features of educational apps include interactive learning activities, multimedia resources, progress tracking, assessments, collaboration tools, and access to e-books and other learning materials (Fitria, 2024). As essential tools in modern education, these applications enhance the learning experience, making it more dynamic, adaptable, and accessible (Ramli, 2024).

The adoption of educational mobile applications at the university level in Nigeria has progressively increased as smartphones and mobile internet penetration have increased (Muazu & Bishir, 2024). Moodle, Google Classroom, Zoom, Udemy, and Coursera are some of the most popular Learning Management Systems (LMS) for online courses, assignments, and evaluations (Sari & Putri, 2022). Institutions such as the University of Lagos (UNILAG) and Covenant University have developed their own applications for administrative tasks such as registration, getting course materials, and reviewing results. Mobile applications also enable material distribution via digital libraries, such as the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) app and test preparation services like Pass.NG. Furthermore, apps such as WhatsApp, Telegram, Slack, and Microsoft Teams promote communication and collaborative learning between students and lecturers, allowing for group discussions, project work, and academic collaboration. These tools have become essential in enhancing teaching, learning, and administrative efficiency in Nigerian tertiary education (Alimi, 2018; Ojugo & Eboka 2018; Ibrahim & Jibia, 2024).

Learner-Centered Instructional Strategies Used at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

A learner-centered approach is an educational philosophy that prioritizes the student's needs, abilities, interests, and learning styles, shifting the focus from traditional teacher-led instruction to a more student-driven experience (Dove & Schultz, 2018). Unlike traditional methods where the instructor is the primary source of knowledge and students are passive recipients, this approach emphasizes active participation, student engagement, autonomy, and the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills (El Hammoumi et al., 2021). The learner-centred approach improves academic achievement while also encouraging lifetime learning skills and holistic development by focussing on individual needs and active engagement (Hartman, 2020). Despite the challenges in implementation, its benefits make it a valuable strategy in modern education, promoting a more inclusive, engaging, and effective learning experience.

Learner-centered instructional strategies are increasingly regarded as essential for enhancing the quality of tertiary education, especially in Nigeria. Unlike traditional teacher-centered methods, this approach focuses on active student participation, critical thinking, and the application of knowledge in real-world contexts (Enemuoh, 2022). The adoption of a

learner-centered approach in Nigerian tertiary institutions aligns with global educational reforms aimed at fostering autonomous learning and improving student outcomes (Eimuhi & Eimuhi, 2018).

The learner-centered approach includes various tactics that prioritise students' needs, interests, and active engagement. Problem-based learning (PBL) is a crucial technique in which students work together to solve complicated real-world problems, encouraging critical thinking and practical problem-solving abilities (Ibrahim, 2022). Another popular method is the Flipped Classroom, which involves students reviewing lecture materials at home and using classroom time for interactive activities and conversations, allowing them to study at their speed while increasing in-class engagement. Inquiry-based learning enables students to investigate and research ideas or problems, focussing on curiosity and active exploration (Onojah et al., 2020). Flipped classrooms have been proved in study to increase student involvement and academic accomplishment, making them a feasible option for large courses offered in Nigerian colleges.

Collaborative Learning is students working in groups to achieve common goals, which improves teamwork skills and peer learning. Differentiated Instruction tailors instructional methods and resources to accommodate different learning styles, talents, and interests, ensuring that all students can learn in ways that are appropriate for their particular requirements (Ismail & Al Allaq, 2019; Ramasamy, 2024). Self-Directed Learning encourages students to take responsibility for their own learning by fostering goal setting, time management, and independent resource seeking. Experiential Learning offers practical, hands-on experiences, such as internships and simulations, to promote reflective learning and real-world skill development (Pacheco-Velazquez et al., 2024).

Formative assessment entails continuing evaluations that provide feedback and guide education, assisting in identifying learning gaps and adjusting teaching tactics (Angelo & Zakrajsek, 2024). Allowing Student Choice and Autonomy allows students some influence over their learning, which boosts motivation and engagement by allowing them to select topics, projects, or assessments (Hurdle et al., 2024). Finally, scaffolding provides temporary support structures to help students complete tasks, progressively diminishing aid as they gain competency, resulting in increased confidence and independence in their learning. Together, these tactics produce a learning environment that is more sensitive to students' needs while also encouraging active, successful, and personalized learning experiences (Lechón Vásquez, 2024).

Constructivist Learning Theory and Integration of Mobile Applications at the Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Constructivist Learning Theory is an educational philosophy based on the idea that learners construct their understanding and knowledge of the world through experiences and reflecting on those experiences (Bada & Olusegun, 2015). It is rooted in the work of several key theorists, including Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky, and Jerome Bruner. This theory emphasizes active, student-centered learning where students build their knowledge rather than passively receiving information from the teacher (Melissa & Assia, 2022).

Integration of Key Principles of Learner-Centered Instructional Strategies and Constructivist Approaches Using Mobile Educational Applications

Student Autonomy and Constructing Knowledge: Mobile applications can significantly enhance student autonomy and knowledge construction in Nigerian tertiary institutions. These applications empower students to take control of their learning by allowing them to select topics of interest, set learning goals, and choose how to engage with the content. Through features like customizable learning paths and reflective journals, students can build on prior knowledge and actively construct new understanding (Schumacher & Czerwinski, 2014; Ismail et al., 2018). This aligns with constructivist principles, enabling learners to adjust their mental models as they interact with new information (Pardjono, 2016).

Active and Engaged Learning: Mobile applications are pivotal in fostering active and engaged learning, which is at the core of both learner-centered and constructivist approaches. In Nigerian tertiary education, apps that offer simulations, interactive activities, and problem-based learning scenarios allow students to actively apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts (Lee, 2022; Vanhorn et al., 2019). Students are more likely to remain interested and remember learning when they participate in discussions, collaborative projects, and hands-on activities made possible by mobile apps (Bonk & Cunningham, 2012).

Personalized and Contextual Learning: The ability of mobile applications to provide personalized and contextual learning experiences is crucial for addressing the diverse needs of students in Nigeria. These apps can tailor content delivery to individual learning styles, pace, and interests, making learning more relevant and effective (Bonk & Cunningham, 2012). Furthermore, mobile apps can deliver contextual learning opportunities by integrating academic knowledge with real-world applications. Through case studies, field activities, and contextual assignments presented via apps, students can engage with authentic tasks that make learning more meaningful and applicable to their future careers (Hwang et al., 2023).

Collaboration and Social Interaction: Mobile applications enhance collaboration and social interaction, essential elements of learner-centered and constructivist education. In the Nigerian context, where large class sizes can limit direct interaction, apps can provide platforms for group work, peer reviews, and collaborative problem-solving activities (Jamrus & Razali, 2019).

Features such as discussion forums and group projects within mobile apps promote social learning by enabling students to exchange ideas, discuss content, and work together to refine their understanding (Beal & Hontvedt, 2023).

Holistic Development and Scaffolding: Mobile applications can support the holistic development of students by integrating features that promote not just academic skills but also emotional, social, and ethical growth. For instance, apps that include mindfulness exercises, ethical dilemmas, and social skill-building activities contribute to the overall development of the learner (Bonk & Cunningham, 2012). Additionally, these apps can offer scaffolding by providing step-by-step guidance, hints, and adaptive learning pathways that adjust to the learner's proficiency level (Hung et al., 2013; Ikawati, 2020). This ensures that students receive the necessary support as they progress towards greater independence.

Summary

The shift towards integrating mobile applications in Nigerian tertiary institutions has transformed traditional teaching models into learner-centered approaches. Mobile applications provide dynamic platforms for active and engaged learning, allowing students to construct knowledge, collaborate, and access personalized learning pathways. These applications are consistent with constructivist learning theory because they include characteristics like simulations, interactive activities, and real-world problem-solving scenarios. Moreover, mobile applications provide scaffolding support and ensure that students remain engaged, offering diverse methods to cater to different learning styles. This study emphasizes the need for Nigerian institutions to strategically incorporate mobile technologies into their curriculum, support faculty in digital pedagogies, and continuously evaluate the impact on student outcomes to create an effective and inclusive learning environment.

Conclusion

The integration of mobile applications in tertiary education in Nigeria has the potential to significantly enhance the effectiveness of learner-centered instructional strategies. These technologies provide engaging and flexible learning experiences that foster active participation, critical thinking, and social collaboration. Mobile applications connect with constructivist ideas, allowing students to construct knowledge and participate in contextual learning, so improving their overall educational experience. To fully harness these benefits, institutions must prioritize strategic integration of mobile technologies, faculty development, and regular evaluation of their impact on learning outcomes. The shift to mobile-based learning reflects a broader transformation in education, preparing students to thrive in an increasingly digital and globalized world.

Recommendations

1. **Comprehensive Curriculum Integration and Institutional Support:** Institutions should establish clear standards for integrating mobile applications into the curriculum, ensuring alignment with learning objectives, course materials, and assessment methods. Additionally, institutional leadership should allocate resources such as funding, technical support, and digital infrastructure to facilitate the integration of mobile learning into instructional practices.
2. **Customizable and Accessible Learning Platforms:** Mobile applications should offer flexible, customizable learning paths that cater to various learning styles and paces, thereby enhancing student engagement. These platforms must also be accessible to all students, including those with disabilities, through features like text-to-speech and customizable interfaces. Ensuring affordability is crucial to providing equal access for all students.
3. **Collaboration with Developers for Localized and Secure Solutions:** Universities should collaborate with developers to create mobile applications tailored to the specific needs of Nigerian students. These partnerships can ensure the development of localized content and relevant resources while prioritizing data privacy and security to protect students' personal and academic information.
4. **Ongoing Monitoring, Evaluation, and Digital Literacy Development:** Institutions should implement procedures for the continuous evaluation of mobile applications, including surveys, focus groups, and analytics, to assess their impact on learning outcomes. Simultaneously, digital literacy programs should be expanded for both students and faculty to ensure effective use of these tools.
5. **Cooperation and Peer Learning Enhancement:** Mobile applications should feature tools that promote peer learning and collaboration, such as discussion boards, group projects, and peer assessments. These collaborative elements help students develop real-world teamwork skills and enhance their overall learning experience.
6. **Lifelong Learning Skills:** Mobile applications should be designed to foster critical thinking, self-directed learning, and problem-solving skills. These capabilities are essential for students' success in an evolving educational and professional landscape.

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